

BEHAVIOR OF GRADIENT DESIGNED COMPOSITE UNDER BALLISTIC IMPACT

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SUMMARY: A ceramic plate is often added to the surface of the polymer composite backing in order to create a mechanism to destroy the projectile and spread the impact energy. In order to lessen the weight of the hard ceramic face plate and introduce additional energy dissipation and defeating mechanisms, a Gradient Design Composite (GDC) was developed; Ceramic spheres are embedded in a matrix to form a face component while the backing plate is composed of Spectra Shield® composite.

The ceramic spheres have the capability of defeating the projectile similar to ceramic plate. The ballistic limit of a GDC composite is a function of sphere size. The bigger the sphere, the bigger the penetration hole, thus improve the ballistic performance by having more backing materials to participate in absorbing the kinetic energy. Visual examination of the experimental panel shows that the backing material have gone through severe delamination and out-of-plane deformation.

KEYWORDS: composite armor, gradient design concept, small arms body armor

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been used successfully as a light weight material for many protective applications under low and high velocity impacts. By proper selection of material systems and design of fiber architecture, it has been shown that a high level of damage containment can be achieved as demonstrated in a compression after impact test [1]. As the velocity of impact and the nature of the impactor changes, as in the case of a very high velocity projectile (~ 3000 ft/s.), a ceramic plate is often added to the surface of the polymer composite backing in order to create a mechanism to destroy the projectile and spread the impact energy over a wide area on the backing plate. Current small arms protective body armor systems used in the U.S. Army frequently consist of a ceramic face backed by fiber reinforced composite. These body armors is used to protect effectively against threats such as .30 caliber type bullets which have a higher and more concentrated energy impact than fragments. In order to lessen the weight of the hard ceramic face plate and introduce additional energy dissipation and defeating mechanisms against the projectile, a Gradient Design Composite (GDC) was developed by a combination of material and geometric hybrid [2].

The Gradient Design Composite - GDC (Fig. 1) is a design concept wherein the material system consists of a harden component, an energy dissipation component and a damage containment component which are organized according to a gradient of varying functions. Ceramic spheres of various sizes are embedded in a matrix of appropriate rigidity to form a face component. The backing plate is composed of fiber reinforced composite with various levels of structural integration.

Fig. 1: Gradient design concept for multifunctional ballistic composites

The goal of a recent study [3] was to verify the ballistic protection of Gradient Design Composite (GDC) consist of aluminum oxide ceramic spheres as a hard/facing layer and Spectra Shield® as a backing layer. The target zone for armor protection was: areal density between 6.0 to 10.0 lb/ft² and Ballistic protection based on “Military Standard V50 Ballistic Test for Armor, MIL-STD-662E” of 3000-4000 ft/s.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Experimental Design

The experimental design of the research program was aimed to verify the ballistic protection performance of the GDC with areal density between 6.0 to 10.0 lb/ft². A two layer composite armor of a ceramic sphere layer bonded by epoxy and a Spectra Shield backing could be designed with various sphere sizes and thickness of ceramic layer and backing plate offering a range of protection levels. An analytical model developed by Florence [4], was modified and employed for predicting ballistic limit velocities in the experimental design stage.

$$V_{50} = [\sigma_o \epsilon H_b \pi R^2 (1 + \psi) / 0.91 m_p]^{1/2}$$

where, the values used in the computations were the following

V_{50} : the ballistic limit of the armor

σ_o : the ultimate tensile strength of the backing plate, 3.0 x 10⁹ Pa (Spectra® 1000 fiber tensile strength was used in calculation for estimation of an ultimate strength of Spectra Shield® backing plate.)

ϵ : the rupture strain of the backing plate, 3.4% (Spectra® 1000 fiber breaking elongation was used in the calculation)

H_c, H_b : the thickness of the ceramic tile and back-up plate, respectively.

ρ_c, ρ_b : densities of ceramics and backing composite materials, respectively; 2610 kg/m³ for aluminum oxide sphere layer, 3400 kg/m³ for ceramic tile and 1000 kg/m³ for Spectra backing layer

m_p : the projectile mass.

m_t : the mass of the target involved in the penetration, varies depending on the thickness of the two layers process, $m_t = \pi R^2 (\rho_c H_c + \rho_b H_b)$

Ψ : the ratio of m_t/m_p

R : the radius of the zone of the target affected by the impact

r : the projectile radius, 3.81 mm.

A constant impact target zone of $R=17.5$ mm was used for all the experimental panels. This value is based on previous test information [2]. Fig. 1 shows predicted V50 as function of the weight of the experimental panels. The panels with areal density below 6.0 lb/ft² were added to evaluate the backing (Spectra Shield®) only. The experimental panels with areal density above 10.0 lb/ft² were added to allow investigation of 3 layer sphere structures. Table 1 provides detailed description and predicted performance of the experimental panels. Spectra Shield® layers varied from 105 to 145. One, two, and three layers of ceramic spheres were used while two sizes of spheres: 7/32" or 1/2". The V50 performance of the panels were predicted to be from around 3000 to 4000 ft/s based on Florence's model [4] in which the value of R , the radius of the target zone affected by the projectile, used was 17.5 mm for all the experimental panels.

Materials and Panel Fabrication

Spectra Shield® was provided in roll form [0/90], 54" wide, weighing 3.8 oz/yd² or 0.027 lb/ft² per ply. The Spectra Shield® prepregs were prepared with Kraton thermoplastic resin, which is a copolymer of styrene and butadiene produced by Shell.

Fig. 2: Experimental panels - predicted V50 vs. areal density

Table 1: Experimental panels - predicted performance

Panel No.	No. of Spectra Shield	Layers Spheres (7/32")	Predicted Areal Density (lb/ft ²)	Performance V50 (ft/s)
1-3	145	0	3.991	2923
4-6	105	1	5.855	2859
7-9	125	1	6.405	3229
10	145	1	6.956	3593
13	105	2	8.82	3367
16-17	125	2	9.37	3768
22-23	105	1 (1/2")	9.667	3499
27	105	3	11.785	3808

A specially designed steel mold was used to make 12"x12" ballistic testing samples. Dake Hot Press was used for hot pressing the prepregs. Thermocouples were used to monitor the temperature of the upper and lower platens and Frekote 700-NC releasing agent by The Dexter Corporation was used for mold release.

The Spectra Shield® prepregs were stacked to desired number of layers/total areal density using the following empirical equations

$$\text{Thickness of the panel(in)} = N (\# \text{ of plies}) \times 0.0053 \text{ (in, thickness/ply)} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Areal Density (lb/ft}^2\text{)} = 4.9 \times \text{thickness of the panel (in)} \quad (3)$$

The layers were placed into the hot mold (125°C) for 20 minutes under constant press of 125 Psi, and observe the temperature of the filled mold maintained at 120°C. Then the panel was let to cool down to 100°C under pressure and removed from the mold.

Processing of the Sphere/Hard Facing Layer

As mentioned before, in order to see the effect of aluminum oxide spheres size as hard facing plate, two sizes were selected: 7/32" and 1/2", these spheres were fabricated into 1,2 or 3 layers. Fig 3. shows the arrangement of 7/32" ceramic spheres. In the case of 1/2" spheres (panel No. 22 and 23), in order to fill the gaps between the spheres a smaller size (1/8") spheres were added as filler as seen in Fig. 4. The spheres were bonded to each other as well as to the backing material by epoxy (Shell Epon Resin 828 and Shell Epi-Cure 3282). The spheres and epoxy were placed on the bottom of the mold, and then the spheres were evenly arranged and distributed to maximize the packaging density inside the mold. At this stage, a Spectra Shield Panel made by hot press was placed into the mold on top of the sphere mixture. Then the mold was closed, and placed on the press for curing under pressure of 500 Psi. To get the desired mechanical properties, all the assembled armors were post cured under 100°C for 2 hours.

Fig. 3: Arrangement of 7/32” ceramic spheres

Fig. 4: 1/2” spheres and 1/8” spheres as filler

Panel Properties

Table 2 list the structure and physical properties of the experimental samples that were made for the study.

Table 2: Experimental panels - structure and physical properties

Panel No.	Spectra Layer	Spheres layer/size	Spectra Thickness (in)	Spheres Thickness (in)	Total Thickness (in)	Spectra Weight (lb)	Spheres Weight (lb)	Total Weight (lb)
1	145	0	0.833	-	0.833	3.950	-	3.950
4	105	1/ 7/32”	0.602	0.228	0.831	2.838	3.084	5.92
7	125	1/ 7/32”	0.722	0.227	0.949	3.418	3.088	6.51
10	145	1/ 7/32”	0.838	0.226	1.064	3.975	3.125	7.10
13	105	2/ 7/32”	0.603	0.439	1.042	2.860	5.556	8.416
16	125	2/ 7/32”	0.720	0.452	1.171	3.419	5.446	8.87
23	105	1/ 1/2”	0.607	0.541	1.147	2.885	7.085	9.97
27	105	3/ 7/32”	0.603	0.755	1.358	2.877	8.509	11.386

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Ballistic Testing

Ballistic testing were carried out at H. P. White Laboratory, Inc. in accordance with the “Military Standard V50 Ballistic Test for Armor, MIL-STD-662E”. The projectile used for the testing was 7.62 mm M60 Ball type with a lead core encased in a brass jacket. The projectile weighs about 7 to 9 grams. The exact type and weight of the projectile are proprietary information.

A machine gun was used for the firing. The samples were rigidly mounted by heavy duty clamps with the area of impact normal to the line of fire. A witness plate made of 0.002” thick aluminum sheet was located 6 inch behind and parallel to the test sample. Four electronic counter type chronograph measuring devices were used to measure the velocity of the projectile.

One to four shots were fired on each sample. The location of the next shot was selected upon inspecting the target after the previous shot. The normal up-and-down firing procedure was

used. In this study, the ballistic limit V50 is defined as the average of the highest partial penetration velocity and the lowest complete penetration velocity. Table 3 shows the results obtained in the ballistic testing.

In the case of Panel No. 10, and 27, the V50 values were incalculated due to a missing data: either partial penetration or complete penetration information was unavailable. In these cases the high partial or the low complete projectile velocity were chosen to represent the ballistic performance of the experimental panel. Fig. 5 shows the ballistic performance of the GDC panels.

Table 3: Summary of ballistic testing results

Panel No.	Spectra Layer	Spheres layer/size	Average Thickness (in)	Average Weight (lb)	Number of Shots	V50	High Partial	Low Complete
1,2,3	145	0	0.839	3.95	6	2456	2372	2551
4,5,6	105	1/ 7/32"	0.835	5.91	4	2943	2900	3000
7,8,9	125	1/ 7/32"	0.952	6.51	2	3493	3428	3557
10	145	1/ 7/32"	1.070	7.10	2	Incalculable	NA	3560
13	105	2/ 7/32"	1.036	8.40	2	3527	3472	3582
16,17	125	2/ 7/32"	1.176	8.85	2	3583	3549	3617
22,23	105	1/ 1/2"	1.156	9.97	2	3703	3674	3732
27	105	3/ 7/32"	1.302	11.37	2	Incalculable	3794	NA

Fig 5: V50 results of the experimental panels

Figures 6-A,B,C,D, and E shows the penetration hole created on the facing (sphere) layer.

Fig. 6A: Penetration hole panel No. 1 (no spheres)

Fig. 6B: Penetration hole panel No. 5 (1 layer)

Fig. 6C: Penetration hole panel No. 17 (2 sphere layers)

Fig. 6D: Penetration hole panel No. 27 (3 layers)

Fig. 6E: Penetration hole panel No. 23 (1/2'')

Table 4 contains information regarding the size (diameter) of the penetration hole from the front and the thickness of the Spectra Shield® layers that did not showed evidence of delamination (pre-delamination thickness). These results shows the direct relationship between the sphere size and sphere layers on the front penetration hole. Fig. 6 illustrated the relation between the number of sphere layers and the size of the penetration hole. There are no evidence that the Spectra Shield® layer - the backing layer influence the size of the penetration hole.

Fig. 7 - A and B shows typical delamination and Out-of plane deformation of the Spectra Shield® layer as observed from the back side of the experimental panels after the ballistic testing. Taking into the consideration the difficulties in measuring and averaging the intact layer (as reported in Table 5) it is clearly evident that the bigger the penetration hole size, the delimitation region start earlier due to decrease in the projectile velocity.

Table 4 Penetration hole and pre-delamination thickness

Panel No.	Spectra Shield®	Spehers layer/size	Penetration Hole Diameter Size (mm)	Pre-Delamination Thickness inch/number of layers
1,2,3	145	0	4.66	0.551/104
4,5,6	105	1/ 7/32"	15.58	0.353/67
7,8,9	125	1/ 7/32"	14.99	0.384/72
10	145	1/ 7/32"	14.36	0.532/100
13	105	2/ 7/32"	23.14	0.260/49
16,17	125	2/ 7/32"	20.92	0.369/70
22,23	105	1/ 1/2"	35.18	0.230/43
27	105	3/ 7/32"	27.71	0.468/88

Fig.7: Typical Delamination and Out-of plane deformation of the Spectra Shield®
 A - Panel No. 2 and B - Panel No. 16

COMPARISON OF RESULTS WITH PREDICTION

Experimental V50 as well as the predicted V50 based on Florence's model of the experimental panels are listed in Table 5. Only the experimental panels with both facing/sphere layer and backing/Spectra Shield® layer are listed. The last column in Table 5 shows the difference between the experimental V50 and the predicted V50 (% Difference = (V50 Experimental - V50 Predicted)/V50 Experimental). It is clear that the modified Florence model with several simplifying assumptions provide a good prediction regarding the ballistic velocities at the experimental design stage. However, when measuring R - the radius of the zone of the target affected by the impact and recalculate V50 values based on the penetration hole size as listed in Table 5 a totally different values for V50 are obtained. Table 6, lists the predicted V50 from Florence's model based on:

- cone radius from previous study (R=17.5mm)
- actual measured value of the cone radius.

Table 5: V50 -Experimental vs. Prediction

Panel No.	Spectra Layer	Spheres layer/size	V50 Experimental	V50 Predicted	% Difference
4,5,6	105	1/ 7/32"	2943	2859	+2.8
7,8,9	125	1/ 7/32"	3493	3229	+7.6
10	145	1/ 7/32"	Incalculable <3560	3593	-0.9
13	105	2/ 7/32"	3527	3367	+4.5
16,17	125	2/ 7/32"	3583	3768	-5.2
22,23	105	1/ 1/2"	3703	3499	+5.5
27	105	3/ 7/32"	Incalculable >3794	3808	-0.3

In order to overcome the above limitation, it is suggested to try and introduce a geometric factor into Florence's model. The geometric factor could provide a link between the material and geometric parameters of the ceramic spheres and the ballistic limits. more experimental results are needed to explore the values of this suggested factor and relay them with the spheres size, shape and packaging.

Table 6: V50 - 2 Predictions

Panel No.	Spectra Layer	Spheres layer/size	V50 Predicted R=17.5 mm	Actual R	V50 Predicted R=actual
4,5,6	105	1/ 7/32"	2859	7.79	792
7,8,9	125	1/ 7/32"	3229	7.50	834
10	145	1/ 7/32"	3593	7.18	862
13	105	2/ 7/32"	3367	11.57	1632
16,17	125	2/ 7/32"	3768	10.46	1539
22,23	105	1/ 1/2"	3499	17.59	3536
27	105	3/ 7/32"	3808	13.86	2494

CONCLUSIONS

The ceramic spheres have the capability of defeating the projectile similar to ceramic tiles as evident by the flattening of the projectile. The fracture cone radius varied according to the sphere radius and energy dissipation was through the breaking up of the ceramic spheres and failure of the backing composite by shearing, fiber cutting and extensive delamination. The ballistic limit of a GDC composite is a function of sphere size. The bigger the sphere, the bigger the penetration hole, thus improve the ballistic performance by having more backing materials to participate in absorbing the kinetic energy. Visual examination of the experimental panel after the ballistic testing shows that the backing material (Spectra Shield® composite) have gone through severe delamination and out-of-plane deformation.

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